

Effect of Radiation, Absorption on Unsteady Double Diffusive Convection Flow of a Viscous Dissipative Chemically Reacting Fluid in a Vertical Channel

M.Nagasasikala¹ and Prof.A.Leelarathnam²

¹Lecturer in Mathematics,K.S.N,Government Degree College for Women,Anantapur,A.P

²Department of Applied Mathematics,S.P.Mahila University,Tirupathi,A.P

ABSTRACT

An attempt has been to investigate the unsteady thermal convection due to the imposed traveling thermal wave on the boundaries of a vertical channel. The effects of free convective heat and mass transfer flow has been discussed by solving the governing unsteady non-linear equations under perturbation scheme with the aspect ratio δ as a perturbation parameter.. The velocity, the temperature and the concentration have been analyzed for different variations of the governing parameters Sc, Q_1, N, Ec, k and $z+\gamma t$. The rate of heat and mass transfer have been evaluated and tabulated for different sets of parameters.

Keywords: Traveling thermal waves, Heat and Mass transfer, Thermal radiation, chemical reaction, Radiation absorption, Heat sources

INTRODUCTION

There are many transport processes in nature and in many industries where flows with free convection currents caused by the temperature differences are affected by the differences in concentration or material constitutions. In a number of engineering applications foreign gases are injected to attain more efficiency, the advantage being the reduction in wall shear stress, the mass transfer conductance or the rate of heat transfer. Gases such as H_2, H_2O, Co_2 , etc., are usually used as foreign gases in air flowing past bodies. So the problems of heat and mass transfer past vertical bodies in boundary layer flows have been studied by many of whom the names of Somers(1956), Gil et al(1965), Adeams and Lowell(1968) and Gebhart and Peera(1971) are worth mentioning. The mass transfer phenomenon in unsteady free convective flow past infinite vertical porous plate was also studied by Soudalgekar and Wavre(1977) and Hossain and Begum(1985).

The combined effects of thermal and mass diffusion in channel flows has been studied in the recent times by a few authors notably. Nelson and wood (1989,1986). Lee et al(1982), Miyatake and Fujii (1973,1974), Sparrow et al (1984) and others (1992,1978,1996). Nelson and Wood(1986) have presented numerical analysis of developing laminar flow between vertical parallel plates for combined heat and mass transfer natural convection with uniform wall temperature and concentration boundary conditions. For along channel (low Rayleigh numbers) the numerical solutions approach the fully developed flow analytical solutions. At intermediate Rayleigh numbers it is observed that the parallel plate heat and mass transfer is higher than that for a single plate. Yan and Lin (1988) have examined the effects of the latent heat transfer associated with the liquid film vapourization on the heat transfer in the laminar

forced convection channel flows. Results are presented for an air-water system under various conditions. The effects of system temperature on heat and mass transfer are investigated. Recently Atul Kumar Singh et al (2003) investigated the heat and mass transfer in MHD flow of a viscous fluid past a vertical plate under oscillatory suction velocity. Convection fluid flows generated by traveling thermal waves have also received attention due to applications in physical problems. The linearised analysis of these flows has shown that a traveling thermal wave can generate a mean shear flow within a layer of fluid, and the induced mean flow is proportional to the square of the amplitude of the wave. From a physical point of view, the motion induced by traveling thermal waves is quite interesting as a purely fluid-dynamical problem and can be used as a possible explanation for the observed four – day retrograde zonal motion of the upper atmosphere of Venus. Also, the heat transfer results will have a definite bearing on the design of oil or gas –fired boilers.

Vajravelu and Debnath (1986) have made an interesting and a detailed study of non-linear convection heat transfer and fluid flows, induced by traveling thermal waves. The traveling thermal wave problem was investigated both analytically and experimentally by Whitehead (1972) by postulating series expansion in the square of the aspect ratio (assumed small) for both the temperature and flow fields. Whitehead (1972) obtained an analytical solution for the mean flow produced by a moving source. Theoretical predictions regarding the ratio of the mean flow velocity to the source speed were found to be in good agreement with experimental observations in Mercury which therefore justified the validity of the asymptotic expansion a posteriori. Ravindra (1994) has analysed the mixed convection flow of a viscous fluid through a porous medium in a vertical channel. The thermal buoyancy in the flow field is created by a traveling thermal wave imposed on the boundaries. Purushothama Reddy (1995) has analysed the unsteady mixed convective effects on the flow induced by imposing traveling thermal waves on the boundaries. Nagaraja (1973) has investigated the combined heat and mass transfer effects on the flow of a viscous fluid through a porous medium in a vertical channel, with the traveling thermal waves imposed on the boundaries while the concentration is maintained uniform on the boundaries. Sivanjaneya Prasad(2002) has analysed heat and mass transfer effects on the flow of an incompressible viscous fluid through a porous medium in vertical channel. Sulochana et al have considered the unsteady convective heat and mass transfer through a porous medium due to the imposed traveling thermal wave boundary through a horizontal channel bounded by non –uniform walls. Tanmay Basak et al(2006) have analysed the natural convection flows in a square cavity filled with a porous matrix for uniformly and non-uniformly heated bottom wall and adiabatic top wall maintaining crust temperature of cold vertical walls. Darcy – Forchheimer model is used to simulate the momentum transfer in the porous medium. Guria and Jana(2006) have discussed the two dimensional free and forced convection flow and heat transfer in a vertical wavy channel with traveling thermal waves embedded in a porous medium. The set of non-linear ordinary differential equations are solved analytically. The velocity and temperature fields have been obtained using perturbation technique. Reddaiah et al(2010) have discussed the effect of radiation on unsteady convective heat transfer flow of a viscous fluid through in porous medium in a vertical channel with traveling thermal wave and heat sources.

In this paper we consider the unsteady thermal convection due to the imposed traveling thermal wave on the boundary in a vertical channel bounded by flat walls. The effects of free convective heat and mass transfer flow has been discussed by solving the governing unsteady non-linear equations under perturbation scheme. The velocity, the temperature and the concentration have been analysed for different variations of the

governing parameters. The rate of heat and mass transfer have been evaluated and tabulated for these sets of parameters.

FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

We consider the motion of viscous, incompressible fluid in a vertical channel bounded by flat walls. The thermal buoyancy in the flow field is created by a traveling thermal wave imposed on the boundary wall at $y=L$ while the boundary at $y = -L$ is maintained at constant temperature T_1 . The walls are maintained at constant concentrations. A uniform magnetic field of strength H_0 is applied transverse to the walls. Assuming the magnetic Reynolds to be small we neglect the induced magnetic field in comparison to the applied magnetic field. Assuming that the flow takes place at low concentration we neglect the Duffor effect. The Boussinesq approximation is used so that the density variation will be considered only in the buoyancy force. The viscous and Darcy dissipations are taken into account to the transport of heat by conduction and convection in the energy equation. Also the kinematic viscosity ν , the thermal conducting k are treated as constants. We choose a rectangular Cartesian system $O(x, y)$ with x -axis in the vertical direction and y -axis normal to the walls. The walls of the channel are at $y = \pm L$.

The equations governing the unsteady flow and heat transfer are

Equation of linear momentum

$$\rho_e \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) - \rho g - (\sigma \mu_e^2 H_0^2) u \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_e \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

Equation of continuity

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Equation of energy

$$\rho_e C_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) = \lambda \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) + Q + \mu \left(\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right) + \left(\frac{\mu}{\lambda k} + \sigma \mu_e^2 H_0^2 \right) (u^2 + v^2) + Q_1 (C - C_e) \quad (4)$$

Equation of Diffusion

$$\left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right) = D_1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} \right) - k_1 (C - C_e) \quad (5)$$

Equation of state

$$\rho - \rho_e = -\beta \rho_e (T - T_e) - \beta^* \rho_e (C - C_e) \quad (6)$$

where ρ_e is the density of the fluid in the equilibrium state, T_e , C_e are the temperature and Concentration in the equilibrium state, (u, v) are the velocity components along $O(x, y)$ directions, p is the pressure, T, C are the temperature and Concentration in the flow region, ρ is the density of the fluid, μ is the constant coefficient of viscosity, C_p is the specific heat at constant pressure, λ is the coefficient of thermal conductivity, k is the permeability of the porous medium, D_1 is the molecular diffusivity, Q_1 is the radiation absorption coefficient, β is the coefficient of thermal expansion, β^* is the volume expansion with mass

fraction, k_1 is the chemical reaction coefficient, Q is the strength of the constant internal heat source, σ is electrical conductivity of the medium magnetic permeability, μ_e is magnetic permeability and q_r is the radiative heat flux.

The flow is maintained by a constant volume flux for which a characteristic velocity is defined as

$$q = \frac{1}{L} \int_{-L}^L u \, dy. \quad (8)$$

The boundary conditions for the velocity and temperature fields are

$$\begin{aligned} u = 0, v = 0, T = T_1, C = C_1 \quad \text{on } y = -L \\ u = 0, v = 0, T = T_2 + \Delta T_e \sin(mx + nt), C = C_2 \quad \text{on } y = L \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\Delta T_e = T_2 - T_1$ and $\sin(mx + nt)$ is the imposed traveling thermal wave

In view of the continuity equation we define the stream function ψ as

$$u = -\psi_y, v = \psi_x \quad (10)$$

Eliminating pressure p from equations (2)&(3) and using the equations governing the flow in terms of ψ are

$$\left[(\nabla^2 \psi)_t + \psi_x (\nabla^2 \psi)_y - \psi_y (\nabla^2 \psi)_x \right] = \nu \nabla^4 \psi - \beta g (T - T_0)_y - \beta^* g (C - C_0)_y - \left(\frac{\sigma \mu_e^2 H_0^2}{\rho_e} \right) \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} \quad (11)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \rho_e C_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) = \lambda \nabla^2 T + Q + \mu \left(\left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 \right) + \\ + \left(\frac{\mu}{k} + \left(\frac{\sigma \mu_e^2 H_0^2}{\rho_e} \right) \right) \left(\left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right) + Q_1 (C - C_e) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (12)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right) = D_1 \nabla^2 C - k_1 C \quad (13)$$

Introducing the non-dimensional variables in (11) - (13) as

$$x' = mx, y' = y/L, t' = t \nu m^2, \Psi' = \Psi/\nu, \theta = \frac{T - T_e}{\Delta T_e}, C' = \frac{C - C_1}{C_2 - C_1} \quad (14)$$

the governing equations in the non-dimensional form (after dropping the dashes) are

$$\delta R \left(\delta (\nabla_1^2 \psi)_t + \frac{\partial(\psi, \nabla_1^2 \psi)}{\partial(x, y)} \right) = \nabla_1^4 \psi - \left(\frac{G}{R} \right) (\theta_y + N C_y) - M^2 \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} \quad (15)$$

The energy equation in the non-dimensional form is

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \delta P \left(\delta \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} \right) = \nabla_1^2 \theta + \alpha + \left(\frac{PR^2 E_c}{G} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 + \delta^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 \right) + \\ + (M^2) \left(\delta^2 \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right) + Q_1 C \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (16)$$

The Diffusion equation is

$$\delta S c \left(\delta \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right) = \nabla_1^2 C - k C \quad (17)$$

where

$$R = \frac{qL}{\nu} \text{ (Reynolds number), } G = \frac{\beta g \Delta T_e L^3}{\nu^2} \text{ (Grashof number)}$$

$$P = \frac{\mu C_p}{k_1} \text{ (Prandtl number), } E_c = \frac{\beta g L^3}{C_p} \text{ (Eckert number)}$$

$$\delta = mL \text{ (Aspect ratio), } \gamma = \frac{n}{\nu m^2} \text{ (non-dimensional thermal wave velocity)}$$

$$Sc = \frac{\nu}{D_1} \text{ (Schmidt Number), } N = \frac{\beta^* \Delta C}{\beta \Delta T} \text{ (Buoyancy ratio)}$$

$$Q_1 = \frac{Q_1' \Delta C L^2}{\Delta T k_1} \text{ (Radiation absorption parameter),}$$

$$M^2 = \frac{\sigma \mu_e^2 H_o^2 L^2}{\nu^2} \text{ (Hartmann Number), } k = \frac{k_1 L^2}{D_1} \text{ (Chemical reaction parameter)}$$

$$\nabla_1^2 = \delta^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}$$

The corresponding boundary conditions are

$$\psi(+1) - \psi(-1) = -1$$

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = 0, \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} = 0 \text{ at } y = \pm 1 \tag{18}$$

$$\theta(x, y) = 1, C(x, y) = 0 \text{ on } y = -1$$

$$\theta(x, y) = \text{Sin}(x + \pi), C(x, y) = 1 \text{ on } y = 1$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} = 0, \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} = 0 \text{ at } y = 0 \tag{19}$$

The value of ψ on the boundary assumes the constant volumetric flow in consistent with the hypothesis (8). Also the wall temperature varies in the axial direction in accordance with the prescribed arbitrary function t .

ANALYSIS OF THE FLOW

The main aim of the analysis is to discuss the perturbations created over a combined free and forced convection flow due to traveling thermal wave imposed on the boundaries. The perturbation analysis is carried out by assuming that the aspect ratio δ to be small.

We adopt the perturbation scheme and write

$$\psi(x, y, t) = \psi_0(x, y, t) + \delta \psi_1(x, y, t) + \delta^2 \psi_2(x, y, t) + \dots$$

$$\theta(x, y, t) = \theta_0(x, y, t) + \delta \theta_1(x, y, t) + \delta^2 \theta_2(x, y, t) + \dots$$

$$C(x, y, t) = C_0(x, y, t) + \delta C_1(x, y, t) + \delta^2 C_2(x, y, t) + \dots \tag{20}$$

On substituting (20) in (16) - (17) and separating the like powers of δ the equations and respective conditions to the zeroth order are

$$\psi_{0,yyyy} - M_1^2 \psi_{0,yy} = \frac{G}{R} (\theta_{0,y} + N C_{0,y}) \tag{21}$$

$$\theta_{0,yy} + \alpha + \frac{PE_c R^2}{G} (\psi_{0,yy})^2 + \frac{PE_c M_1^2}{G} (\psi_{0,y}^2) + Q_1 C_0 = 0 \tag{22}$$

$$C_{o,yy} - (kSc)C_0 = 0 \tag{23}$$

with $\psi_{0(+1)} - \psi_{0(-1)} = -1$,

$$\psi_{0,y} = 0, \psi_{0,x} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = \pm 1 \tag{24}$$

$$\theta_o = 1, C_0 = 0 \quad \text{on } y = -1$$

$$\theta_o = \sin(x + \pi), C_0 = 1 \quad \text{on } y = 1 \tag{25}$$

and to the first order are

$$\psi_{1,yyyy} - M_1^2 \psi_{1,yy} = \frac{G}{R}(\theta_{1,y} + NC_{1,y}) + (\psi_{0,y} \psi_{0,xyy} - \psi_{0,x} \psi_{0,yy}) \tag{26}$$

$$\theta_{1,yy} = (\psi_{0,x} \theta_{o,y} - \psi_{0,y} \theta_{ox}) + \frac{2PE_c R^2}{G} (\psi_{0,yy} \psi_{1,yy}) + \left. \begin{aligned} &+ \frac{2PE_c M_1^2}{G} (\psi_{0,y} \psi_{1,y}) - Q_1 C_1 \end{aligned} \right| \tag{27}$$

$$C_{1,yy} - (kSc)C_1 = (\psi_{0,x} C_{o,y} - \psi_{0,y} C_{ox}) \tag{28}$$

with

$$\psi_{1(+1)} - \psi_{1(-1)} = 0$$

$$\psi_{1,y} = 0, \psi_{1,x} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = \pm 1 \tag{29}$$

$$\theta_1(\pm 1) = 0, C_1(\pm 1) = 0 \quad \text{at } y = \pm 1 \tag{30}$$

Assuming $Ec \ll 1$ to be small we take the asymptotic expansions as

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_0(x, y, t) &= \psi_{00}(x, y, t) + Ec\psi_{01}(x, y, t) + \dots \\ \psi_1(x, y, t) &= \psi_{10}(x, y, t) + Ec\psi_{11}(x, y, t) + \dots \\ \theta_0(x, y, t) &= \theta_{00}(x, y, t) + \theta_{01}(x, y, t) + \dots \\ \theta_1(x, y, t) &= \theta_{10}(x, y, t) + \theta_{11}(x, y, t) + \dots \\ C_0(x, y, t) &= C_{00}(x, y, t) + C_{01}(x, y, t) + \dots \\ C_1(x, y, t) &= C_{10}(x, y, t) + C_{11}(x, y, t) + \dots \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

Substituting the expansions(31) in equations (21)-(23) and separating the like powers-of Ec we get the following

$$\theta_{00,yy} = -\alpha - Q_1 C_{00}, \quad \theta_{00}(-1) = 1, \theta_{00}(+1) = \sin D_1 \tag{32}$$

$$C_{00,yy} - (kSc)C_{00} = 0, \quad C_{00}(-1) = 0, C_{00}(+1) = 1 \tag{33}$$

$$\psi_{00,yyyy} - M_1^2 \psi_{00,yy} = \frac{G}{R}(\theta_{00,y} + NC_{00,y}), \tag{34}$$

$$\psi_{00(+1)} - \psi_{00(-1)} = 1, \psi_{00,y} = 0, \psi_{00,x} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = \pm 1$$

$$\theta_{01,yy} = -\frac{PR}{G} \psi_{00,yy}^2 - \frac{PM_1^2}{G} \psi_{00,y}^2 - Q_1 C_{01}, \quad \theta_{01}(\pm 1) = 0 \tag{35}$$

$$C_{01,yy} - (kSc)C_{01} = 0, \quad C_{01}(-1) = 0, C_{01}(+1) = 0 \tag{36}$$

$$\psi_{01,yyyy} - M_1^2 \psi_{01,yy} = \frac{G}{R}(\theta_{01,y} + NC_{01,y}) \tag{37}$$

$$\psi_{01(+1)} - \psi_{01(-1)} = 0, \psi_{01,y} = 0, \psi_{01,x} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = \pm 1$$

$$\theta_{10,yy} = GP(\psi_{00,y} \theta_{00,x} - \psi_{00,x} \theta_{00,y}) - Q_1 C_{10}, \quad \theta_{10}(\pm 1) = 0 \tag{38}$$

$$C_{10,yy} - (kSc)C_{10} = Sc(\psi_{00,y}C_{00,x} - \psi_{00,x}C_{00,y}) \quad C_{10}(\pm 1) = 0 \quad (39)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \psi_{10,yyyy} - M_1^2 \psi_{10,yy} &= \frac{G}{R}(\theta_{10,y} + NC_{10,y}) + \\ &+ (\psi_{00,y}\psi_{00,yy} - \psi_{00,x}\psi_{00,yy}) \\ \psi_{10}(+1) - \psi_{10}(-1) &= 0, \psi_{10,y} = 0, \psi_{10,x} = 0 \text{ at } y = \pm 1 \end{aligned} \right| \quad (40)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \theta_{11,yy} &= P(\psi_{00,y}\theta_{01,x} - \psi_{01,x}\theta_{00,y} + \theta_{00,x}\psi_{01,y} - Q_1C_{11} \\ - \theta_{01,y}\psi_{0,x}) - \frac{2PR^2}{G}\psi_{00,yy}\psi_{10,yy} - \frac{2PM_1^2}{G}\psi_{00,y}\psi_{10,y}, \theta_1(\pm 1) &= 0 \end{aligned} \right| \quad (41)$$

$$C_{11,yy} - (kSc)C_{11} = Sc(\psi_{00,y}C_{01,x} - \psi_{01,x}C_{00,y} + C_{00,x}\psi_{01,y} - C_{01,y}\psi_{0,x}) \quad (42)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \psi_{11,yyyy} - M_1^2 \psi_{11,yy} &= \frac{G}{R}(\theta_{11,y} + NC_{11,y}) + (\psi_{00,y}\psi_{11,yy} - \\ &- \psi_{00,x}\psi_{01,yy} + \psi_{01,y}\psi_{00,yy} - \psi_{01,x}\psi_{00,yy}) \\ \psi_{11}(+1) - \psi_{11}(-1) &= 0, \psi_{11,y} = 0, \psi_{11,x} = 0 \text{ at } y = \pm 1 \end{aligned} \right| \quad (43)$$

The equations (32)-(43) are solved algebraically subject to the boundary conditions.

NUSSELT NUMBER and SHERWOOD NUMBER

The local rate of heat transfer coefficient (Nusselt number Nu) on the walls has been calculated using the formula

$$Nu = \frac{1}{\theta_m - \theta_w} \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} \right)_{y=\pm 1}$$

and the corresponding expressions are

$$(Nu)_{y=+1} = \frac{(d_{65} + Ecd_{67} + \delta d_{69})}{(\theta_m - \sin(D_1))} \quad (Nu)_{y=-1} = \frac{(d_{66} + Ecd_{68} + \delta d_{70})}{(\theta_m - 1)}$$

$$\theta_m = d_{71} + Ecd_{72} + \delta d_{73}$$

The local rate of mass transfer coefficient (Sherwood number)(Sh) on the walls has been calculated using the formula

$$Sh = \frac{1}{C_m - C_w} \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right)_{y=\pm 1}$$

and the corresponding expressions are

$$(Sh)_{y=+1} = \frac{(d_{74} + \delta d_{76})}{(C_m - 1)} \quad (Sh)_{y=-1} = \frac{(d_{75} + \delta d_{77})}{(C_m)}$$

$$C_m = d_{78} + \delta d_{79}$$

where d_1, \dots, d_{77} constants

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

In this analysis we discuss the combined influence of radiation absorption, chemical reaction on unsteady convective heat and mass transfer flow of a viscous dissipative fluid in a

vertical channel under the influence of the uniform magnetic field. The unsteady flow is due to the traveling thermal waves imposed on the boundaries.

The non-linear coupled equations governing the flow heat and mass transfer are solved by a perturbation technique with aspect ratio δ and Eckert number Ec as perturbation parameters.

The axial velocity (u) is shown in figs (1 – 8) for different values of Sc , N , k , Q_1 , Ec . The actual axial flow is in the vertically upward direction and hence $u < 0$ represents a reversal flow.

Fig (1) represents u with Schmidt number Sc . It is found that the flow exhibits a reversal flow in the entire flow region with $Sc = 0.24$ and for higher $Sc = 0.6$ it is confined to the regions adjacent to $y = \pm 1$ and for still higher $Sc \geq 1.3$ it disappears in the entire flow region. $|u|$ depreciates with increase in $Sc \leq 0.6$ and enhances with higher $Sc \geq 1.3$. With respect to buoyancy ratio N we find that when the molecular buoyancy force dominates over the thermal buoyancy force $|u|$ depreciates when the buoyancy forces act in the same direction and for the forces acting in opposite direction it enhances in the flow region (fig 2). The variation of u with chemical reaction parameter γ and radiation absorption parameter Q_1 is shown in fig (3). An increase in k or Q_1 leads to an enhancement in u in the entire flow region. Fig (4) represents u with Eckert number Ec . It is found that higher the dissipative heat smaller the axial velocity in the flow region.

The secondary velocity (v) which arises due to the non-uniform boundary temperature is shown in figs (5-8) for different parametric values. It is observed that the secondary velocity v is directed towards the mid region for all variations. From fig(5) we find that $|v|$ enhances with increase in Sc thus lesser the molecular diffusivity larger $|v|$ in the entire flow region. When the molecular buoyancy force dominates over the thermal buoyancy force $|v|$ enhances in the entire flow region when the buoyancy forces act in the same direction and for the forces acting in opposite direction it depreciates in the flow region (fig 6). With respect to γ and Q_1 we find an enhancement in $|v|$ with increase in k or Q_1 . Thus the effect of radiation absorption is to enhance the magnitude of v in the flow region (fig 7). The variation of v with Eckert number Ec is shown in fig(8). It is found that higher the dissipative heat larger $|v|$ in the left half and smaller in the right half of the channel .

The non-dimensional temperature distribution (θ) is shown in figures (9 – 12) for different parametric values. We follow the convention that the non-dimensional temperature is positive or negative according as the actual temperature is greater/lesser than T_2 . From fig(9) we observe that lesser the molecular diffusivity ($Sc \leq 0.6$) larger the actual temperature and for further lowering of the diffusivity smaller the temperature in the flow region. The variation of θ with buoyancy ratio N shows that the actual temperature reduces with $N > 0$ and enhances with $|N| (<0)$ (fig 10). The variation of θ with chemical reaction parameter k indicates that the actual temperature reduces with increase in $k \leq 2.5$ and enhances with $k \geq 3.5$ (fig 11). Fig(12) shows that the effect of radiation absorption is to decrease the actual temperature in the flow region. The graphs of θ with Eckert number Ec indicates that higher the dissipative heat smaller the actual temperature in the flow region (fig 13).

Fig. 1 : Variation of u with Sc
 I II III IV

Fig. 2 : Variation of u with N
 I II III IV
 N 1 2 -0.5 -0.8

Fig. 3 : Variation of u with k & Q_1
 I II III IV V
 k 0.5 1.5 2.5 0.5 0.5
 Q_1 1.5 1.5 1.5 2.5 3.5

Fig. 4 : Variation of u with Ec
 I II III IV
 Ec 0.02 0.04 0.06 0.09

Fig. 5 : Variation of v with Sc
 I II III IV
 Sc 0.24 0.6 1.3 2.01

Fig. 6 : Variation of v with N
 I II III IV
 N 1 2 -0.5 -0.8

Fig. 7 : Variation of v with k & Q_1

I	II	III	IV	V	
k	0.5	1.5	2.5	0.5	0.5

Fig. 8 : Variation of v with Ec

I	II	III	IV	
Ec	1	2	-0.5	-0.8

Fig. 9 : Variation of θ with Sc

I	II	III	IV	
Sc	0.24	0.6	1.3	2.01

Fig. 10 : Variation of θ with N

I	II	III	IV	
N	1	2	-0.5	-0.8

Fig. 11 : Variation of θ with k

I	II	III	IV	
k	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5

Fig. 12 : Variation of θ with Q_1

I	II	III	
Q_1	1.5	2.5	3.5

Fig. 13 : Variation of θ with Ec

Fig. 14 : Variation of C with Sc

Fig.15 : Variation of C with N

	I	II	III	IV
N	1	2	-0.5	-0.8

Fig. 16 : Variation of C with k & Q_1

	I	II	III	IV	V
k	0.5	1.5	2.5	0.5	0.5
Q_1	1.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	3.5

Fig. 17 : Variation of C with Ec

	I	II	III	IV
Ec	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.09

The non-dimensional concentration distribution (C) is shown in figures (14-16) for different parametric values. We follow the convention that the non-dimensional concentration is positive or negative according as the actual concentration is greater / lesser than C_2 . With respect to Sc it is observed that lesser the molecular diffusivity larger the actual

concentration in the entire flow region and for further lowering of the diffusivity the concentration reduces in the left half and enhances in the right half (fig 14). With respect to buoyancy ratio N , it is observed that the actual concentration enhances with increase in $N > 0$ and depreciates with $|N|$ (fig 15). The variation of c with chemical reaction parameter k shows that the actual concentration depreciates in the left half and enhances in the right half with increase in $k \leq 2.5$ and enhances with higher $k = 3.5$. The effect of radiation absorption (Q_1) is to enhance the actual concentration in the left half and depreciates it in the right half (fig 16). The variation of c with Ec shows that higher the dissipative heat smaller the actual concentration in the flow region (fig 17).

The rate of heat transfer (Nusselt number) at $y = \pm 1$ is shown in tables (1 – 12) for different parametric values. It is found that the rate of heat transfer enhances with $G > 0$ and depreciates with $G < 0$ at $y = \pm 1$. An increase in R leads to an enhancement in $|Nu|$ at both the walls.

From tables (1 & 3) we find that lesser the molecular diffusivity larger $|Nu|$ and for further lowering of the diffusivity smaller $|Nu|$ at both the walls. When the molecular buoyancy force dominates over the thermal buoyancy force the rate of heat transfer depreciates at $y = \pm 1$ when the buoyancy forces act in the same direction and for the forces acting in opposite direction $|Nu|$ depreciates in the heating case and enhances in the cooling case.

An increase in chemical reaction parameter $\gamma \leq 2.5$ results in a depreciation in $|Nu|$ at $y = \pm 1$ and for higher $\gamma = 3.5$ we notice an enhancement in $|Nu|$ at $y = +1$ and a depreciation at $y = -1$. With respect to Q_1 we find the rate of heat transfer at $y = +1$ depreciates for $G > 0$ and enhances for $G < 0$ with $Q_1 \leq 1.5$ and for higher $q_1 \geq 2.5$ it enhances for $G > 0$ and it reduces for $G < 0$. At $y = -1$, the rate of heat transfer depreciates with increase in $Q_1 \leq 1.5$ and enhances with higher $Q_1 \geq 2.5$ (Tables 5 & 11). The variation of Nu with Ec shows that at $y = +1$ $|Nu|$ depreciates for $G > 0$ and enhances for $G < 0$ with $Ec \leq 0.04$ and for higher $Ec = 0.06$ it enhances for $G > 0$ and depreciates for $G < 0$. While at $y = -1$ $|Nu|$ depreciates with $Ec \leq 0.06$ and enhances with higher $Ec = 0.09$. (table.2&4). The rate of mass transfer at $y = \pm 1$ is evaluated for different values of Sc , k and $x + \gamma t$ and is shown in tables 5&6. It is found that the rate of mass transfer enhances at $y = +1$ and reduces at $y = -1$ with increase in Sc . Thus lesser the molecular diffusivity larger $|Sh|$ at $y = +1$ and smaller at $y = -1$... With respect to chemical reaction parameter k we find that the rate of mass transfer at $y = +1$ enhances in the heating case and reduces in the cooling case while at $y = -1$ $|Sh|$ reduces with $k \leq 1.5$ and for further higher $k \geq 2.5$ it reduces in the heating case and enhances in the cooling case. The variation of Sh with the phase $x + \gamma t$ of the boundary temperature shows that an increase in $x + \gamma t \leq \pi$ reduces $|Sh|$ at $y = +1$ and enhances at $y = -1$ and for higher $x + \gamma t \geq 2\pi$ we notice an enhancement at $y = +1$ and depreciation at $y = -1$ (Tables 5&6).

Table.1
Nusselt number (Nu) at $y = +1$

G	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
100	-3.0292	-6.2198	-1.6362	-1.1316	-1.8364	-1.2303	-1.1831
300	-0.1616	-5.6171	-1.6550	-0.5485	-5.8629	-0.6678	-0.6104
-100	0.5880	-10.0260	-1.6174	-1.3094	-1.3998	-2.0848	-2.2073
-300	0.9695	18.3427	-1.5986	-1.3799	-0.9616	-10.6254	-42.4669
Sc	0.24	0.6	1.3	2.01	1.3	1.3	1.3
N	1	1	1	1	2	-0.5	-0.8

Table.2
Nusselt Number(Nu) at y=1

G	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X
100	-1.6362	-2.0284	-3.3203	-4.6579	-1.4341	-1.3268	-1.4514	-0.8592	-0.7833	-0.7914
300	-1.6550	-1.3087	-3.2420	-4.9022	-0.0837	-4.1023	-3.1343	0.4080	0.3518	0.7742
-100	-1.6174	-3.2798	-5.6409	-4.0005	-1.6868	-1.7636	-1.6023	-1.1581	-1.1043	-1.1411
-300	-1.5986	-6.3028	2.7378	-2.3190	-5.4461	-1.1880	-1.0196	-1.1324	-1.0750	-1.1013
Q1	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Ec	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.09	0.02	0.02	0.02
k	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5						

Table.3
Nusselt number (Nu) at y = -1

G	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
100	-1.9449	-2.9956	-1.7085	0.3240	0.3854	0.1605	0.1436
300	-0.1553	-3.3925	-1.7390	-1.0798	1.6639	-0.5536	-0.5309
-100	0.1450	-6.0286	-1.6776	0.5752	0.3582	0.5820	0.6247
-300	0.0180	2.1908	-1.6464	-0.0526	-0.1333	3.3898	1.6253
Sc	0.24	0.6	1.3	2.01	1.3	1.3	1.3
N	1	1	1	1	2	-0.5	-0.8

Table.4
Nusselt Number(Nu) at y=1

G	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X
100	-1.7085	-0.4428	-1.5439	-1.8747	0.0990	-0.0873	-0.3988	0.3402	0.3650	0.4263
300	-1.7390	-0.5734	-1.5949	-2.5118	-1.3767	1.9240	3.8540	-2.0899	-3.9704	-2.2728
-100	-1.6776	-0.3476	-1.7091	14.5546	0.4192	0.4087	0.6886	0.7539	0.9195	0.9035
-300	-1.6464	-0.5050	0.5268	0.6143	0.0626	0.9508	1.4588	-12.7350	1.0952	1.0375
Q1	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Ec	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.09	0.02	0.02	0.02
k	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5						

Table.5
Sherwood number (Sh) at y = +1

Sc	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
0.24	-2.5044	-2.6016	-3.1457	-3.8601	-2.5003	-2.4946	-2.5060
0.6	-2.5190	-4.1394	-6.8194	-10.5469	-2.4976	-2.4678	-2.5273
1.3	-3.3985	-10.7174	-8.8910	-2.4593	-3.2565	-3.0700	-3.4555
2.01	-4.9870	-9.4170	-1.3648	-0.5496	-4.3683	-3.6875	-5.2659
k	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
x + γt	$\pi/4$	$\pi/4$	$\pi/4$	$\pi/4$	$\pi/2$	π	2π

Table.6
Sherwood number (Sh) at y = -1

Sc	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
0.24	4.0036	1.2239	0.6681	0.4301	4.0039	4.0044	4.0035
0.6	1.4905	0.3538	0.1120	-0.0021	1.5096	1.5365	1.4832
1.3	0.5246	-0.1141	-0.3611	-1.1850	0.6222	0.7642	0.4877
2.01	0.1380	-0.5387	1.2657	0.0862	0.3598	0.6969	0.0560
k	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
x + γt	$\pi/4$	$\pi/4$	$\pi/4$	$\pi/4$	$\pi/2$	π	2π

REFERENCES

1. Adams,J.A and Lowell, R.L : *Int.J.Heat and Mass transfer*, V.11. p.1215 (1968)
2. Atul Kumar Singh , Ajay Kumar Singh ,N.R. Singh, “Heat and Mass transfer in MHD flow of a viscous fluid past a vertical plate under oscillatory suction velocity. *Ind .J. Pure application maths* 34(3) :429-442, March 2003
3. Gebhart,B and Peera,L:*Int.J.Heat and Mass transfer* ,V.15,p.269(1971)
4. Gebhart,B and Peera,L:*Int.J.Heat and Mass transfer*,V.14,p.2024(1971)
5. Gill,W.N,Delesal,E and Zec,D.W:*Int.J.Heat and Mass transfer* , V.8, p.1131 (1965)
6. Guria,M and Jana,R.N:Hydrodynamic flows through vertical wavy channel with traveling thermal waves embedded in porous medium,*Int.J.Appl.Math and Mech*,V.11,N0.3,pp.609-621(2006)
7. Hossain,M.A and Begum,R.A:*Appl.Space Sci*,V.15,p.145(1985)
8. Lee,T.S., Parikh, P.G., Archivos ,A.Bershader,D *Int.J. Heat and mass transfer*, V.25, PP.499-511 (1982).
9. Miyatake, O and Fujii, T: *Heat Transfer – Jap, Res.*, V.25, PP. 25-23 (1973).
10. Miyatake, O and Fujiim T: *Heat Transfer- Jap, Res*, V.3 pp 29-33 (1974).
11. Nagaraja, P :*Heat and Mass Transportation in time dependent flows through channels*, Ph.D. thesis S.K.University, Anantapur, India (1973).
12. Nelson D.J and Wood, B.D, : Combined heat and mass transfer natural convection between vertical parallel plates, *Intl. J. Heat and Mass transfer*, V.32, PP.1779-1787 (1989).
13. Nelson D.J. and Wood B.D : *J. Heat transfer* V.4, PP-1587-1582. (1986).
14. P. Reddaiah and D. R. V. Prasada Rao, Finite Element Analysis Of A Non-Darcy Magnetohydrodynamic Mixed Convective Heat And Mass Transfer Of A Viscous Fluid Through A Porous Medium In A Cylindrical Annulus With Heat Sources, *Int. J. of Appl. Math and Mech.* 6 (14): 32-50, 2010.
15. Puroshotama reddy, Y :Unsteady mixed convection flows through vertical channel with varying gap. Ph.D thesis S.K.Univeristy, Anantapur, India (1995).
16. Ravindra, M :MHD convection flow through a porous medium with non-uniform wall temperature, Ph.D thesis, S.K.University, Anantapur, India (1994).
17. Salah El -Dih ,M.M : *Int. concentration heat mass transfer* v.19, P.239 (1992).
18. Sivanjaneya Prasad, P :Effects of convective heat and mass transfer on unsteady hydromagnetic channel flows, Ph.D, thesis, S.K.University, Anantapur , India(2002).
19. Somers,E.V.:*J.Appl.Mech*,V.23,p.295(1956)
20. Soundelgekar,V.M and Wavre,P.P:*Heat and mass transfer*, V.20, p.1363 (1977)
21. Soundelgekar,V.M and Wavre,P.P:*Heat and mass transfer*, V.20, p.1303 (1978)

22. Sparrow, E.M and Azevedo, L.F.A :*J Heat Transfer*, V.106, PP.325-332 (1984).
23. Sparrow, E.M and Azevedo, L.F.A :*J Heat Transfer*, V.28, PP. 1847-1857 (1985).
24. Sulochana et al : Connective Heat and Mass Transfer through a porous medium in channels –A finite Element approach, Ph.D thesis submitted to S.K.University, Anatapur.
25. Tanmay Basak, S.Roy,T.Paul,I.Pop, Natural convection in a square cavity filled with a porous medium. Effects of various thermal boundary conditions. *Intl. J.of Heat and mass transfer* 49 (2006) 1430-1441.
26. Vajravelu, K and Debnath, L : Non –Linear study of convective heat transfer and fluid flows induced by traveling thermal waves ,*Acta Mech*, V.59, PP-233-249 (1986).
27. Wei-Mon Yan : *Int. J. Heat and Mass transfer* V.37 , No.13, PP :1857-1866(1994).
28. Wei-Mon Yan : *Int. J. Heat and Mass transfer* V.39 ,No.1 ,PP.1479-1488 (1996).
29. White head, J.A : *Geo Physics fluid dynamics* V.3, PP.161-180 (1972).
30. Wirtz, R.A and Stutzaman, R.t :*J. Heat transfer*, V.104 ; PP.501 -507 (1982).
31. Yan, W.M and Lin, T.F : Combined heat and mass transfer in laminar forced convection channel flows, *Int. Heat and Mass Transfer*, V.15 PP.333-343 (1988).